

1 Study of the performance of a cylindrical flow-through
2 electro-Fenton reactor using different arrangements of
3 carbon felt electrodes: effect of key operating parameters

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17 Keywords: electro-Fenton, carbon felt electrodes, electrochemical disinfection,
18 amoxicillin, fecal coliforms.

19 **Abstract**

20 In this work, a cylindrical flow-through electro-Fenton reactor containing graphite felt
21 electrodes and an Fe(II) loaded resin was evaluated for the production of the Fenton
22 reaction mixture and for the degradation of amoxicillin (AMX) and fecal coliforms
23 containing aqueous solutions. First, the influence of several factors such as treatment
24 time, current intensity, flow rate and electrode position were investigated for the
25 electrogeneration of H₂O₂ and the energetic consumption by means of a factorial design
26 methodology using a 2⁴ factorial matrix. Electric current and treatment time were found
27 to be the pivotal parameters influencing the H₂O₂ production with contributions of 40.2
28 and 26.9%, respectively. The flow rate had low influence on the responses, however,
29 500 mL min⁻¹ (with an average residence time of 1.09 min obtained in the residence time
30 distribution analysis) allowed to obtain a better performance due to the high mass
31 transport to and from the electrodes. As expected, polarization was also found to play an
32 important role, since for the cathode-to-anode flow direction, lower H₂O₂ concentrations
33 were observed when compared with the anode-to-cathode flow arrangement, indicating
34 that part of the H₂O₂ produced in the cathode was destroyed at the anode. A fluorescence
35 study of hydroxyl radical production on the other hand, showed that higher yields were
36 obtained using an anode-to-cathode flow direction (up to 3.88 μM), when compared with
37 experiments carried out using a cathode-to-anode flow path (3.11 μM). The removal of
38 a commercial formulation of the antibiotic AMX was evaluated in terms of total organic
39 carbon, achieving up to 57.9 % and 38.63% of pollutant mineralization using synthetic
40 and real sanitary wastewater spiked, respectively. Finally, the efficiency of the process
41 on the inactivation of fecal coliforms in sanitary wastewater samples was assessed,
42 reducing 90% of the bacteria after 5 min of electrolysis.

43 Introduction

44 Electrochemical advanced oxidation processes (EAOPs) constitute an attractive
45 approach to treat wastewater effluents contaminated with persistent pollutants. These
46 processes are characterized by the use of hydroxyl radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$) which are strong
47 oxidant species capable of attacking a wide variety of organic contaminants ($E^\circ = 2.8\text{ V}$
48 vs. standard hydrogen electrode, SHE) (Comninellis 1994; Brillas et al. 2009; Brillas
49 2020). Among the different EAOPs, the so-called electro-Fenton processes are quite
50 promising since they are based on the *in situ* electro-generation of H_2O_2 by means of the
51 $2e^-$ reduction of dissolved oxygen at a suitable cathode material under acid or alkaline
52 conditions (see Eq. (1) -(2)), and in the presence of an iron promoter as shown in Eq. (3)
53 (Salmerón et al. 2021).

57 Since the electro-Fenton process involves electrochemical reactions, its performance is
58 limited by the mass transport of oxygen and the pollutant species to the electrode surface
59 and therefore it is closely related to the reactor design (Garcia-Segura et al. 2020). Over
60 the last years, the design of most of the continuous-flow electro-Fenton reactors has
61 focused on the flow-by configuration, where the pollutant containing effluent flows
62 parallel to the anode and cathode surfaces (Zhou et al. 2017). In these systems,
63 convection becomes negligible near the electrode-solution interface and therefore, in
64 order to reduce the mass transport limitations of the conventional flow-by reactors, it is
65 important to incorporate fluid mixer promoters such as mechanical agitators or pumps.

66 In this way, flow-through electro-Fenton reactors stand out as an attractive option to
67 overcome these weaknesses since the solution flows through porous anode and cathode
68 electrodes, increasing mass transport events that result in improved electrochemical
69 conversion, current efficiency and reduced energy consumption (Zhou et al. 2017). In
70 flow-through electro-Fenton reactors, 3D porous electrodes have shown good yields in
71 the abatement of several pollutants (Jiao et al. 2020; Yu et al. 2020) and among the
72 electrodes employed, carbonaceous materials, such as graphite felt, stand out as
73 desirable electrodes because of their stability, electric conductivity, high surface area,
74 chemical resistance, efficient cathodic regeneration of Fe(II) as well as its inherent
75 filtration characteristics (Brillas et al. 2009; Panizza and Oturan 2011; Zhou et al. 2012,
76 2014, 2017; Petrucci et al. 2016).

77 Due to these features, the performance of flow-through electro-Fenton reactors has been
78 extensively reported. For instance, Ren et al. (2016) studied the degradation of tartrazine
79 in a vertical-flow electro-Fenton reactor, made up 10 cell compartments using a PbO_2
80 anode and a modified graphite felt mesh cathode. Those authors reported the complete
81 abatement of the pollutant and 61% of total organic carbon (TOC) removal at pH 3, using
82 a voltage of 4.0 V, a flow rate of 40 mL min^{-1} , and a concentration of 0.4 mM Fe(II) (Ren
83 et al. 2016). In a subsequent study, Ren et al. (2020) also reported the treatment of real
84 domestic sewage using a stacked flow-through electro-Fenton reactor equipped with
85 modified graphite felt cathodes and dimensionally stable anode (DSA) mesh anodes.
86 Applying 2.5 V and using 0.4 mM Fe(II) these authors obtained a bacterium inactivation
87 value of $\log 3.34\text{--}3.46$ and efficient removals of COD, N-NH_3 and total phosphorus (Ren
88 et al. 2020). Also, Chai et al. (2021) evaluated a coupled system of flow-through electro-
89 Fenton and electrosorption processes for the treatment of high-salinity organic
90 wastewater using iron, Ti and activated carbon felt electrodes. In this work, the authors
91 achieved removal values of chemical oxygen demand (COD), total nitrogen and salinity
92 of 96.5, 98.2, and 46.2%, respectively (Chai et al. 2021). The modification of activated
93 carbon fibers coupled to a DSA anode in a flow-through electro-Fenton process for
94 orange II dye abatement, has also been reported by Jiao et al. (2020) (Jiao et al. 2020).

95 As it can be seen, from these and other reports, good yields on pollutant removal are
96 obtained using flow-through electro-Fenton configurations. However, the use of anodes
97 such as iron, PbO_2 or DSA and the need to add Fe(II) as the Fenton mixture promoter,
98 limit the use of these reactors in large-scale applications and in this context, flow-through
99 electro-Fenton reactors equipped with electrodes made of affordable carbonaceous
100 materials and where the Fe(II) is provided and retained by an ion exchange resin, has
101 also been reported by our research group (García-Espinoza et al. 2019; Robles et al.
102 2020; García-Espinoza et al. 2021).

103 In spite of the interest in 3D and flow-through reactors, there is still a severe lack on the
104 understanding of reactor configuration effects since most electrochemical publications
105 focus on novel electrode materials rather than on recognizing the significant influences
106 of mass transport on pollutant degradation (García-Segura et al. 2020). In this way, the
107 flow direction of the solution is an important operational variable in flow-through reactors
108 because it can control the overall performance of the process. This is the case of the
109 electrochemical elimination of N-NH_4 , in which by arranging an anode-to-cathode flow is
110 possible to achieve its removal and obtain safe N_2 , since in the anode, the oxidation of
111 N-NH_4 to NO_2^- and NO_3^- is achieved, prior to its subsequent reduction to N_2 in the

112 cathode. This sequence of reactions is not obtained in the cathode-to-anode flow
113 configuration (Heck et al. 2019; Garcia-Segura et al. 2020; Ren et al. 2020).

114 The performance of the electro-Fenton process has also been tested for the degradation
115 of biorecalcitrant pollutants (Komtchou et al. 2015; García-Espinoza et al. 2019; Castillo-
116 Monroy et al. 2020; Droguett et al. 2020; Puga et al. 2021). Among them, the elimination
117 from aquatic media of antibiotic compounds such as amoxicillin (AMX) is relevant since
118 this a pharmaceutical compound that is widely used in human and veterinary medicine
119 (aus der Beek et al. 2016). In water, AMX is rapidly degraded by biotic and abiotic factors,
120 yielding different intermediate products which are suspected to be more resistant to
121 degradation, and potentially more toxic, than the parent compound (Elizalde-Velázquez
122 et al. 2016; Loos et al. 2018). Furthermore, AMX may bioaccumulate in fish muscle
123 tissues, which results in the potential presence of this pharmaceutical compound in food,
124 leading to a passive consumption of the antibiotic that may result in undesirable effects
125 on consumer health such as immunoallergic responses. However, the main problem
126 related with the presence of the AMX in fish tissues is the possibility of inducing bacterial
127 resistance genes (Elizalde-Velázquez et al. 2016). Furthermore, since 60 to 80% of the
128 substance is excreted without alteration (Sodhi et al. 2021) and the hydrolysis half-life of
129 the AMX in water at pH 7 has been reported to be 19.7 d (Braschi et al. 2013), AMX has
130 been detected in water bodies with concentrations of up to $0.218 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Gros et al. 2013)
131 which is higher than the predicted no-effect concentration (PNEC) of $0.078 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Loos
132 et al. 2018).

133 Due to its physicochemical proprieties such as low LogK_{ow} value, low volatility, high
134 stability, high polarity and complex chemical structure (Table 1), AMX is a persistent
135 compound which may result in eco-toxicological effects and human health affectations
136 (Jones et al. 2002) and therefore, is one compound in the *watch list* of substances being
137 monitored by the European Union (Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2015).

138

139

Table 1. Physicochemical properties of the amoxicillin.

Pharmaceutical group	Aminopenicillin antibiotic
Molecular formula	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}$
CAS	26787-78-0
Chemical structure	
Molecular mass (g mol^{-1})	365.4

Water solubility (mg L ⁻¹)	3.43x10 ³
pKa	3.2, 11.7
LogK _{ow}	0.87
Henry's law constant (atm m ³ mol ⁻¹)	2.49X10 ⁻²¹

140 pKa: acid dissociation constant; logK_{ow}: octanol–water partition coefficient

141 In the context of the interest to develop efficient EAOPs for the degradation of
 142 commercial formulations of biorecalcitrant compounds (Murillo-Sierra et al. 2018; de
 143 Matos et al. 2020; Carrera-Cevallos et al. 2021), the aim of this work was to evaluate the
 144 performance on the degradation of AMX of a flow-through electro-Fenton reactor
 145 equipped with carbon felt electrodes. First, residence time distribution was investigated.
 146 Later, the capability of the electrochemical reactor to generate H₂O₂ was evaluated at
 147 different current intensities, recirculation flow, treatment time and position of the
 148 electrodes, also considering the energetic consumption. Afterwards, the process
 149 effectivity for the mineralization of AMX containing solutions was evaluated under
 150 different experimental conditions. Finally, the process was also tested for the inactivation
 151 of fecal coliforms using real sanitary wastewater.

152

153 **Materials and methods**

154 **Chemicals and solutions**

155 While coumarin and cerium sulphate (IV) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, reagent
 156 grade H₂SO₄, NaCl and Na₂SO₄ were supplied by J.T. Baker. A commercial formulation
 157 of the antibiotic AMX (AMSA, Mexico) in capsule presentation of 500 mg was employed.
 158 For the determination of H₂O₂, solutions were prepared using demineralized water
 159 dissolving 0.05 M of Na₂SO₄ as supporting electrolyte. Using this electrolyte, solutions
 160 of coumarin (0.4 mM) and AMX (0.27 mM) were used. Samples of real sanitary
 161 wastewater pretreated by biological processes were also used (chemical oxygen
 162 demand, COD: 45.6±16, pH 7.7±0.2, conductivity: 0.9 ±0.04 mS cm⁻¹). While the pH of
 163 all solutions was 7.0 ± 0.5, the electric conductivity of the Na₂SO₄ electrolyte and the
 164 sanitary wastewater were 8.8 ± 0.4 and 0.8 ± 0.2 mS cm⁻¹, respectively.

165

166 **Electro-Fenton Reactor**

167 The treatment was carried out using a three-compartment cylindrical reactor made of
 168 Nylamid in which the central section of the reactor (141 cm³), was coupled on each side
 169 to one identical compartment using stainless steel screws (see Fig. 1a). The

170 experimental set-up consisted of the reactor equipped with a power source, a peristaltic
 171 pump, a recirculation tank and an oxygen concentrator (Fig. 1b). Carbon cloth circular
 172 pieces (28 cm² effective area, 0.6 mm thickness, 0.5 Ω in² electrical resistivity) served
 173 as electrical contacts for cylindrical carbon felt electrodes (6 cm diameter, 2.35 cm
 174 length), positioned between the compartments (Fig. 1c and 1d). For the electro-Fenton
 175 assays, while in the compartment next to the cathode a cation exchange resin containing
 176 Fe(II) was placed, the same amount of a Na⁺-activated cation exchange resin was
 177 located in the compartment next to the anode (Fig. 1e). As can be seen in Fig. 1a, the
 178 reactor was fed in such a way that the pollutant solution passed through the three
 179 sections the reactor; that is, across the resin compartments and the polarized cloth and
 180 carbon felt electrodes, flowing towards a receiving tank where the effluent solution was
 181 mixed with the influent solution and from where the solution was pumped by means of a
 182 peristaltic pump. Oxygen was fed to the solution using an oxygen concentrator
 183 (AEROUS, CleanWater Tech.) and a Venturi jet aerator in the inlet line at a constant flow
 184 rate of 250 mL min⁻¹. Electrical current was applied using a power supply (Keithley 2400).
 185 All assays were conducted in batch mode under galvanostatic conditions at room
 186 temperature (25 °C). The working volume of the electrochemical system was 0.5 L.

187

188

189 **Fig. 1.** (a) Electrochemical reactor scheme where C_i represents the different
 190 compartments and (b) schematic diagram of the experimental set-up. (1) oxygen
 191 concentrator, (2) electrochemical reactor, (3) power supply, (4) sample point, (5)

192 recirculation tank, (6) peristaltic pump, (7) recirculation pipe; (c) electrodes placed in the
193 center arrangement, (d) electrodes placed in the extremes arrangement, (e)
194 configuration where resin is placed in C1 and C3 compartments.

195

196 **Experimental set-up and methods**

197 Residence time distribution (RTD) was obtained from a tracer test which was conducted
198 using the pulse injection method. In this experiment, a concentrated solution of NaCl was
199 instantly introduced to the inlet line of the reactor and total dissolved solids (TDS) were
200 measured every 5 s at the outlet of the reactor. The normalized residence time
201 distribution function ($E(t)$) and the average residence time (μ) after the pulse tracer input
202 were obtained using Eqs. (4) and (5), respectively (Martin-Dominguez et al. 2005):

$$203 \quad E(t) = \frac{C(t)}{\int_0^{\infty} C(t)dt} \quad (4)$$

$$204 \quad \mu = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} t C(t)dt}{\int_0^{\infty} C(t)dt} \quad (5)$$

205 In these equations, $C(t)$ corresponds to the tracer concentration evolution at the reactor
206 exit and t is time. Later, a full 2^4 factorial design (FD) was used to investigate the effect
207 of the factors and their interactions on the electrogeneration of H_2O_2 and on the energetic
208 consumption of the process. From the FD, an empirical linear model is obtained (see Eq.
209 (6)):

$$210 \quad Y_j = \beta_0 + \sum \beta_i X_i \quad (6)$$

211 Here, Y_j is the response variable, X_i is the independent variable and β_0 , and β_i ,
212 correspond to the constant and the linear model coefficients, respectively (Aquino et al.
213 2013). Four independent factors were studied: electrolysis time (X_1), current intensity
214 (X_2), recirculation flow (X_3) and the position of the electrodes (X_4). Three of these
215 variables were quantitative factors (X_1 , X_2 and X_3) and one corresponded to a categorical
216 factor (X_4). Sixteen assays were required for the FD. Experimental data was analyzed
217 using the Design Expert® program software (Design Expert 7, Stat-Ease Inc.,
218 Minneapolis). The FD was developed within the range of the independent variables
219 according to Table 2. Once the conditions that maximize the H_2O_2 electrogeneration
220 were determined, the percentage of current efficiency (ϕ) for the production of H_2O_2 was
221 computed using Eq. (7), where n is the number of transferred electrons (2) to produce
222 H_2O_2 via oxygen reduction, F is the Faraday constant ($96\,485\text{ C mol}^{-1}$), $C_{H_2O_2}$ is the H_2O_2

223 concentration (g L^{-1}), V is the volume of the solution (L), $M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$ is the molecular weight of
 224 H_2O_2 (34.01 g mol^{-1}), I is the applied current (A) and t is the treatment time (s) (Ma et al.
 225 2019).

$$226 \quad \phi = \frac{nFC_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}V}{M_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}It} 100 \quad (7)$$

227 The energetic consumption per cubic meter of treated water (EC) was calculated using
 228 Eq. (8) (Brillas and Martínez-Huitle 2015).

$$229 \quad E_c \left(\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{m}^3} \right) = \frac{V I t}{\text{Vol } 1000} \quad (8)$$

230 where V , A , t and Vol correspond to the voltage (V), current (A), time (h) and the volume
 231 of treated water (m^3), respectively. It is important to note that the EC values obtained
 232 only take into account the electricity used in the electrolysis assays, disregarding the
 233 energy required to pump the solutions and that consumed in the oxygen concentrator.

234 **Table 2.** Range and codification of independent variables (X_i).

X_i	Variable	Experimental range	
		Min. value (-)	Max. value (+)
X_1	Electrolysis time (min)	15	30
x_2	Current intensity (mA)	150	300
X_3	Recycling flow rate (mL min^{-1})	375	500
X_4	Electrodes position	Center, C2	Extremes, C1 and C3

235

236 Analytical methods

237 Cerium sulfate (IV) dissolved in an acid solution (H_2SO_4) with phenanthroline as
 238 indicator, was prepared and used along with a calibration curve previously constructed,
 239 to quantitatively determine the concentration of H_2O_2 using a volumetric redox titration
 240 method (Daghrir et al. 2013; Komtchou et al. 2015). Assessment of $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical
 241 production was carried out by measuring the generation of the fluorescent 7-
 242 hydroxycoumarin (7-HC) that results from the selective hydroxylation reaction of
 243 coumarin with the $\cdot\text{OH}$ electrogenerated species. The wavelengths of excitation (λ_{ex}) and
 244 emission (λ_{em}) corresponded to 340 and 456 nm, respectively. Both excitation and
 245 emission slits were fixed at 5 nm. The concentration of $\cdot\text{OH}$ ($C_{\cdot\text{OH}}$, in μM) was determined
 246 by means of Eq. (9) which considers that 29% of all $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals are trapped by coumarin
 247 to produce 7-HC (Tokumura et al. 2011). This equation also considers that 2 mol of $\cdot\text{OH}$
 248 radicals react with 1 mol of coumarin to produce 1 mol 7-HC. Since the slope of the

249 calibration curve, $C_{7\text{-HC}}$, corresponds to the concentration of 7-HC, then C_{OH} can be
250 obtained from the fluorescence intensity at 456 nm, FI_{456} .

251
$$C_{\text{OH}} = \left(\frac{2}{0.29}\right) C_{7\text{-HC}} = 23.45 \times 10^{-3} FI_{456} \quad (9)$$

252 The removal of AMX on the other hand, was determined from the TOC assessment.
253 While spectrophotometric tests were carried out using a DR600 HACH apparatus and
254 the TOC measurements utilizing a Shimadzu TOC LCSN equipment, fluorescence
255 measurements were performed using a Cary Eclipse Agilent spectrophotometer. pH,
256 TDS and dissolved oxygen concentration were measured employing a Thermo Scientific
257 potentiometer model Orion Versa Star Pro. COD and nitrate ion (NO_3^-) concentrations
258 were determined employing HACH reagents.

259

260 Results

261 Hydraulic characterization

262 As it was previously pointed out, RTD measurements were used to investigate the
263 hydraulic characteristics of the flow-through electro-Fenton reactor under study. In a
264 pulse, an amount of tracer is suddenly injected in one shot into the feed-stream entering
265 the reactor. The outlet concentration is then measured as a function of time. Fig. 2 shows
266 the obtained RTD curves at two different flow rates and using the reactor with the
267 electrodes placed in the center (see Fig. 1c) and in the absence of applied current.

268

269 **Fig. 2.** RTD curves at flow rates of (a) 375 and (b) 500 mL min⁻¹. Dotted lines represent
270 the average residence time.

271 The calculated average residence time under both experimental conditions
 272 corresponded to 1.37 and 1.09 min at 375 and 500 mL min⁻¹, respectively (see dotted
 273 lines in Fig. 2); which are shorter than the theoretical retention times (1.6 and 1.2 min for
 274 375 and 500 mL min⁻¹ flow rates, respectively). This reflects that the porous carbon felt
 275 electrodes occupy part of the effective volume of the reactor, thus shortening the time
 276 needed for the solution to reach the outlet. Furthermore, the parabolic shape of the
 277 curves means that there is no by-pass effects in the reactor (Monteil et al. 2021), however
 278 the asymmetric shape of the tails also reflects the presence of stagnant zones (Haoran
 279 et al. 2013). At the highest flow rate, a higher and thinner peak can be observed when
 280 compared with the one obtained at the lower flow rate. This observation suggests that
 281 by increasing the flow rate it is possible to obtain a plug flow behavior and that by
 282 reducing the flow rate, the system behaves as a continuous-stirred tank reactor (Monteil
 283 et al. 2021). To further evaluate the effect of the flow rate on the generation of H₂O₂ for
 284 the proposed flow-through reactor, a FD study was carried out.

285

286 Effect of operational parameters

287 The factorial design matrix, experimental and predicted data for the H₂O₂ generated in
 288 anode-to-cathode flow direction and the calculated energy consumption, are presented
 289 in Table 3. The empirical relationship between the responses and variables are
 290 expressed by the polynomial Eqs. (10)-(11).

$$291 \quad Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} = 10.54 + 1.40X_1 + 1.71X_2 + 0.68X_3 - 1.03X_4 + 8.5 \times 10^{-3}X_1X_2 + 0.25X_1X_3 \\
 292 \quad + 0.46X_1X_4 + 0.37X_2X_3 - 0.66X_2X_4 + 0.20X_3X_4 \quad (10)$$

293

$$294 \quad Y_{\text{EC}} = 2.26 + 0.76X_1 + 1.15X_2 - 0.22X_3 + 0.23X_4 + 0.39X_1X_2 - 0.080X_1X_3 \\
 295 \quad + 0.090X_1X_4 - 0.18X_2X_3 + 0.11X_2X_4 + 0.11X_3X_4 \quad (11)$$

296

297 **Table 3.** Experimental factorial matrix and experimental results.

Exp.	Experimental design					H ₂ O ₂ (mg L ⁻¹)				EC (kWh m ⁻³)		
	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	X ₄	Electrolysis time (min)	Current intensity (mA)	Recycling flow rate (mL min ⁻¹)	Electrodes position	Actual value	Predicted value	Actual value	Predicted value
1	-1	-1	-1	-1	15	150	375	Center	8.30	8.41	0.68	0.77
2	-1	1	-1	-1	30	150	375	Center	9.40	9.77	1.37	1.49
3	-1	-1	1	-1	15	300	375	Center	12.75	12.39	2.42	2.43
4	-1	1	1	-1	30	300	375	Center	13.92	13.79	4.95	4.71

5	1	-1	-1	-1	15	150	500	Center	8.50	8.12	0.64	0.63
6	1	1	-1	-1	30	150	500	Center	10.60	10.48	1.25	1.03
7	1	-1	1	-1	15	300	500	Center	13.00	13.59	1.68	1.58
8	1	1	1	-1	30	300	500	Center	16.10	15.99	3.21	3.54
9	-1	-1	-1	1	15	150	375	Extremes	6.30	6.34	0.86	0.63
10	-1	1	-1	1	30	150	375	Extremes	10.10	9.54	1.71	1.72
11	-1	-1	1	1	15	300	375	Extremes	7.50	7.69	2.60	2.71
12	-1	1	1	1	30	300	375	Extremes	10.60	10.94	5.25	5.35
13	1	-1	-1	1	15	150	500	Extremes	6.70	6.84	0.77	0.92
14	1	1	-1	1	30	150	500	Extremes	10.70	11.05	1.61	1.68
15	1	-1	1	1	15	300	500	Extremes	10.10	9.68	2.33	2.29
16	1	1	1	1	30	300	500	Extremes	14.04	13.93	4.80	4.61

298

299 The coefficient R^2 , defined as the ratio of the explained to the total variation, reflects a
300 measure of the degree of fitting. For a good fit, R^2 should be at least 0.80 (Fu et al. 2007).
301 The obtained R^2 (0.9871 for H_2O_2 generation and 0.9891 for energetic consumption) can
302 be seen to be high for both responses, reflecting that the model describes reasonably
303 well the process performance. This was also confirmed by the determination of adjusted
304 coefficients ($adj-R^2$) characterized by the values of 0.9614 and 0.9674 for H_2O_2
305 production and energetic consumption, respectively. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of
306 the results was also performed to evaluate the significancy of the models (Table 1-S and
307 2-S). Comparison of the actual and predicted values for H_2O_2 electrogeneration and
308 energetic consumption indicates that as expected, the highest yields of H_2O_2 production
309 and energetic consumption are reached when applying the maximum current and
310 treatment time (Fig. 1-S).

311 Fig. 3a on the other hand, shows the values of the effects of the independent factors
312 obtained from the polynomial Eqs. (10) – (11). As can be observed from inspection of
313 this figure, for H_2O_2 electrogeneration, the independent variables, treatment time, current
314 intensity, and recycling flow, show all positive effects (see Table 2). This means that the
315 highest yield of H_2O_2 production is reached when the values of these three independent
316 variables correspond to their high levels. The other independent variable, which
317 corresponds to electrode position, shows a negative effect ($b_{4H_2O_2}=-1.03$). This means
318 that the high level of this variable (electrodes placed at the far-end-positions of the
319 reactor), results in lower H_2O_2 concentrations when compared to the ones obtained when
320 the electrodes are positioned in the central compartment (see Table 2).

321 For energetic consumption (the other dependent variable), the data in Figure 3a shows
322 that treatment time, current intensity and position of the electrodes, show all positive
323 effects ($b_{1EC}=0.76$, $b_{2EC}=1.15$, $b_{4EC}=0.23$). This reflects that when the high level of these

324 variables is used, high energy is required (see Table 2). The recirculation flow on the
325 other hand, is characterized by a negative effect on the response ($b_{3EC}=-0.22$), which
326 means that high energetic consumptions are expected when the low level of this variable
327 is utilized (see Table 2). This means that at high flow rates, the energetic consumption
328 is reduced because mass transfer to the electrodes is favored; a fact that also decreases
329 the potential difference. In order to get further insight from the experimental data; the
330 percentage effect of each factor and their interactions on the responses were calculated
331 using Eq. (12):

$$332 \quad P_i = \left(\frac{b_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^k b_i^2} \right) 100 \quad (i \neq 0) \quad (12)$$

333 where P_i is the percentage contribution of each independent factor i , and where b_i
334 represents the estimation of the main effect of the factor i .

335 As depicted in Fig. 3b, the contribution of the primary effects on H_2O_2 generation
336 corresponds to 26.9%, 40.2%, 6.24% and 14.6% for electrolysis time, current, recycling
337 flow rate and electrodes position, respectively. For energetic consumption on the other
338 hand, the contribution of the same variables corresponds to 26.1%, 59.3%, 2.2% and
339 2.5%. As shown in Fig. 3b, the applied current is the factor with the highest contribution
340 for both responses, followed by treatment time. The preponderant significance of current
341 and treatment time lies in the fact that both parameters are strongly related with the
342 amount of electric charge entering the reactor, that is, a higher number of $2e^-$ oxygen
343 reduction events that result in the electrogeneration of H_2O_2 . Similar results have been
344 reported for the performance of EAOPs (Zaviska et al. 2011, 2012; Daghrir et al. 2014;
345 García-Espinoza et al. 2016, 2018).

346

347 **Fig. 3.** (a) Effect of independent and (b) standardized factors on H₂O₂ electrogeneration
 348 and energetic consumption (X₁: time; X₂: current; X₃: recycling flow; X₄: electrodes
 349 position).

350 Assuming that the maximum concentration of H₂O₂ corresponds to the optimal reactor's
 351 performance, the best operating conditions are: 30 min of electrolysis at 300 mA, 500
 352 mL min⁻¹ as recycling flow rate and arranging the electrodes in the central compartment
 353 of the reactor. Under these optimized conditions, the predicted electrogenerated H₂O₂
 354 concentration proposed by the model corresponds to 15.99 mg L⁻¹, a value which is quite
 355 close to the experimentally obtained one (16.10 mg L⁻¹).

356 Fig. 4a shows the concentration of H₂O₂ on time in the anode-to-cathode flow direction
 357 under oxygen and air saturation conditions. As expected, an oxygen concentration
 358 increase allows to obtain higher yields (2.72 times more) when compared to the values
 359 achieved using air (the corresponding concentration of oxygen in the solution is 30 mgO₂
 360 L⁻¹ under oxygen saturation vs. 7.5 mgO₂ L⁻¹ at air saturation). It is interesting to note
 361 that in the cathode-to-anode flow direction arrangement under oxygen saturation
 362 conditions, lower H₂O₂ concentrations were obtained when compared to the anode-to-
 363 cathode set-up (16.1 and 6.1 mg L⁻¹, respectively). This observation suggests that 62%
 364 of H₂O₂ produced in the cathode is consumed at the anode when this arrangement is
 365 employed as indicated by Eq. (13):

366

367 Similar H_2O_2 concentration values were obtained by (Zhang et al. 2021), who achieved
368 up to 17.68 mg L^{-1} at pH 3 after 120 min of electrolysis using a reticular stainless-steel
369 cathode and a DSA anode.

370 Current efficiencies for H_2O_2 generation were also determined and the resulting data is
371 shown in Fig. 4b. Inspection of the experimental curves reveals that as expected, the
372 current efficiency values are higher in the cathode-to-anode flow direction and in the
373 presence of pure oxygen.

374 On the other hand, it is well documented that the optimal pH value for $\cdot\text{OH}$ production
375 from Fenton reaction mixtures, corresponds to 3 (Sirés and Brillas 2021). Taking into
376 account the economic viability of electro-Fenton processes at neutral pH values
377 however, (Estrada-Arriaga et al. 2016; Olvera-Vargas et al. 2021), all the assays
378 reported in this work were carried out under pH conditions close to those found in real
379 wastewater (pH~7).

380

381 **Fig. 4.** (a) Concentration of electrogenerated H_2O_2 and (b) current efficiency. Black \blacksquare :
382 anode-to-cathode flow configuration with oxygen saturation, red \bullet : anode-to-cathode flow
383 arrangement with air saturation, blue \blacktriangle : cathode-to-anode flow set-up with oxygen
384 saturation. Conditions: 300 mA, 0.05 M Na_2SO_4 electrolyte, pH 7, 500 mL min^{-1}
385 recirculation flow.

386

387 **Assessment of $\cdot\text{OH}$ production**

388 Once the experimental conditions that promote the best H_2O_2 generation were obtained,
389 the production of $\cdot\text{OH}$ was evaluated. Fig. 5 shows the fluorescence intensity and the

390 obtained $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration. Inspection of the experimental data reveals that in the
 391 cathode-to-anode flow direction arrangement, the electro-Fenton process allows to
 392 obtain up to $3.11\ \mu\text{M}$ of $\cdot\text{OH}$ at 5 min of electrolysis, which represents a lower production
 393 of the radical when compared with the one obtained in the anode-to-cathode flow
 394 direction set-up ($3.88\ \mu\text{M}$ of $\cdot\text{OH}$). The higher yields of the anode-to-cathode
 395 configuration can be related with the fact that the washed Fe(II) from the resin in C1
 396 interacts with the electrogenerated H_2O_2 in the cathode positioned after the anode, near
 397 to the outlet of the reactor. Therefore, the residual H_2O_2 in Fig. 4a promotes the
 398 production of $\cdot\text{OH}$ directly at the sample point. On the other hand, the $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration
 399 obtained in the cathode-to-anode flow direction configuration is slightly lower when
 400 compared with the aforementioned configuration. In this way, higher $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration
 401 is expected within the reactor since Fe(II) ions react directly with the electrogenerated
 402 H_2O_2 in the electrode placed at the reactor's inlet. In the absence of Fe(II) (see Fig. 5c
 403 and 5d), the $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration is considerably smaller. The electrochemical oxidation
 404 process with the addition of air in the cathode-to-anode flow direction on the other hand,
 405 allowed to obtain up to $0.42\ \mu\text{M}$ of $\cdot\text{OH}$ and as expected, this value increases with the
 406 addition of pure oxygen ($0.49\ \mu\text{M}$ of $\cdot\text{OH}$). In both cases, $\cdot\text{OH}$ generation can be related
 407 to the monoelectronic reduction of H_2O_2 according the Eq. (14):

409 **Fig. 5.** Fluorescence intensity and $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration in an: (a) Electro-Fenton process,
 410 cathode-to-anode arrangement, (b) anode-to-cathode flow configuration, (c)
 411 electrochemical oxidation process cathode-to-anode flow set-up with air saturation, (d)
 412 electrochemical oxidation process cathode-to-anode flow configuration with oxygen
 413

414 saturation, (e) $\cdot\text{OH}$ concentration under the different experimental conditions, determined
415 at 456 nm (black ■: conditions of (a), red •: conditions of (b), blue ▲: conditions of (c),
416 green ▼: conditions of (d)). 300 mA, 0.4 mM of coumarin in 0.05 M Na_2SO_4 electrolyte,
417 pH 7, 500 mL min^{-1} recirculation flow rate.

418

419 **Degradation of AMX containing solutions**

420 The effectiveness of the electro-Fenton process was also evaluated in terms of the
421 mineralization of AMX containing solutions. To clarify the role of the processes that take
422 place within the system, different experimental conditions were evaluated; namely:
423 adsorption (without current intensity), electro-oxidation (same reactor without using the
424 Fe(II) loaded resin) and electro-Fenton using cathode-to-anode flow and anode-to-
425 cathode flow directions. As shown in Fig. 6a, while the TOC values reflect negligible
426 removal by adsorption, the electrochemical oxidation process results in a value of
427 28.92%. As expected, TOC decrease was largely improved (after 30 min of electrolysis)
428 by the electro-Fenton process using either the anode-to-cathode set-up (45.5%), or the
429 cathode-to-anode arrangement (57.9%). This observation not only confirms that the $\cdot\text{OH}$
430 radical species is generated by Eq. (3), playing the most important role in the
431 mineralization of the solution, but also that the cathode-to-anode configuration allows to
432 obtain the higher yields. For AMX mineralization, the cathode-to-anode configuration
433 allows to obtain higher yields when compared with the anode-to-cathode flow
434 arrangement. This observation can be related to the electrogeneration of $\cdot\text{OH}$ (see Eq.
435 (3)) as follows: the contaminated solution passes through the C1 compartment washing
436 Fe(II) ions from the resin and taking them into the central section of the reactor where
437 dissolved O_2 is reduced to produce H_2O_2 at the cathode. This gives rise to the Fenton
438 mixture which in turn is responsible for the observed AMX abatement. Under these
439 conditions, residual H_2O_2 may be oxidized at the anode.

440 Fig. 6b on the other hand, shows the mineralization efficiency of the cathode-to-anode
441 configured electro-Fenton process for real sanitary wastewater, which was previously
442 contaminated with AMX as described in the experimental section. Using this complex
443 effluent matrix, a 38.6% of mineralization was achieved after 30 min of reaction. The
444 lower effectiveness of the process using this solution is probably related to the presence
445 of soluble organic matter that not only inhibits the electro-generation of H_2O_2 , but also
446 promotes competitive reactions. As it can be noted from the experimental data, the quasi-
447 steady state was reached after 5 mean hydraulic residence times.

448 It is interesting to compare the AMX mineralization data obtained in this study with other
 449 reports using electro-Fenton process. In this way, Kadji et al. (2021) obtained 74% of
 450 AMX mineralization after 180 min of electrolysis, with an initial AMX concentration of
 451 0.082 mM. This value was reduced to 39% using a higher AMX concentration (0.164
 452 mM) due to a competitive consumption of oxidizing $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals between AMX and the
 453 by-products formed during the experiments (Kadji et al. 2021). On the other hand, Garza-
 454 Campos et al. (2018) obtained 55% of AMX mineralization after 240 min of treatment
 455 using a BDD anode and an air diffusion mesoporous carbon cathode (Garza-Campos et
 456 al. 2018). In this contribution, 57.95% AMX mineralization efficiency was obtained after
 457 30 min of treatment which is not only a competitive value when compared with those in
 458 the literature, but also cost-attractive due to the use of affordable carbonaceous materials
 459 in the electrodes. Furthermore, since in the electro-Fenton process the $\cdot\text{OH}$ radical is the
 460 dominant oxidant agent, the acute toxicity of the aqueous solution after the treatment
 461 was reduced in 50% using *Daphnia magna* as a biological indicator (Zhang et al. 2021).
 462 This observation suggests that the degradation of AMX by electro-Fenton reactions,
 463 allows to obtain by-products with lower acute toxicity when compared with the parent
 464 compound.

465

466 **Fig. 6.** TOC removal for AMX degradation assays using a synthetic solution: black ■
 467 electro-Fenton process, cathode-to-anode flow configuration with oxygen saturation, red
 468 ●: electro-Fenton process, anode-to-cathode flow arrangement with oxygen saturation,
 469 blue ▲ electrochemical oxidation process, cathode-to-anode flow set-up with oxygen
 470 saturation, green ▼: adsorption (without current). Using real sanitary wastewater: empty

471 black ■ electro-Fenton process, cathode-to-anode flow arrangement with oxygen
472 saturation. 300 mA, pH 7, 500 mL min⁻¹ recirculation flow rate.

473

474 The concentration of NO₃⁻ was also determined as evidence of the degradation of the
475 antibiotic by means of the electro-Fenton process arranged in the cathode-to-anode
476 configuration. Fig. 7a shows the NO₃⁻ concentration on time, and it can be noted that the
477 ion concentration increases with increasing treatment time up to a concentration of 3.6
478 mg L⁻¹. The presence of NO₃⁻ is explained by the mineralization reaction of AMX (Eq.
479 12), which produces NH₄⁺ that in turn, when interacting with [•]OH radicals, generates NO₂⁻
480 (Eq. 13) and eventually NO₃⁻ (Eq. 14). The presence of nitrate ions in the electrolytic
481 solution, confirms the mineralization of AMX.

485 Fig. 8 depicts a diagram of the pathways that are suggested to take place within the flow-
486 through electro-Fenton reactor under study. In this way, the reduction of dissolved
487 oxygen at the carbon felt cathode to promote H₂O₂ needs to occur along with the
488 concomitant production of [•]OH by the presence of the Fe(II) washed from the iron loaded
489 resin in the C1 compartment of the reactor so that finally, it is possible to obtain CO₂,
490 H₂O and inorganic ions.

491 Although these results provide information on the mineralization of AMX using the flow-
492 through electro-Fenton reactor under study, it is clear that, in order to follow the
493 degradation path of the pollutant and to identify by-products, a specific analytic technique
494 such as HPLC, should be used.

495

496 **Disinfection assays**

497 In order to test the efficiency of the process in the inactivation of fecal coliforms, real
498 sanitary wastewater treated by an anaerobic biodigester and anoxic-aerobic bioreactor
499 was used. Under the optimal conditions of the electro-Fenton reactor, Fig. 7b shows that
500 after 5 min of electrolysis, it was possible to reduce the concentration of the fecal coliform
501 from 24 000 MPN 100 mL⁻¹ to 2400 MPN 100 mL⁻¹ and this value was maintained after
502 30 min of treatment; which means an efficiency of inactivation of microorganisms of 90%.

503 On the other hand, when the water passed through the system in the absence of current,
 504 there was no decrease in fecal coliforms after 5 min and after 30 min, a value of 11 000
 505 MPN 100 mL⁻¹ was obtained; indicating that under these conditions, around 50% of fecal
 506 coliforms can be retained in the reaction system.

507

508

509 **Fig. 7.** (a) NO₃⁻ from AMX degradation and (b) fecal coliforms concentration vs time in
 510 real wastewater. Black ■: electro-Fenton process in cathode-to-anode configuration, red
 511 •: adsorption process.

513

513 **Fig. 8.** Schematic diagram of AMX mineralization within the proposed cylindrical flow-
 514 through electro-Fenton reactor using carbon felt electrodes.

515

516 **Conclusions**

517 The performance of a cylindrical flow-through electro-Fenton reactor using carbon felt
518 electrodes was evaluated. An experimental design methodology was applied to evaluate
519 the effects of four independent variables and to determine the best experimental
520 conditions. Among the studied factors current and treatment time were the most
521 meaningful parameters. The best operational parameters were found to be: current of
522 300 mA during 30 min, 500 mL min⁻¹ of recirculation flow rate, with the electrodes placed
523 in the middle of the reactor and at cathode-to-anode flow direction achieving a H₂O₂
524 concentration of 16.1 mg L⁻¹ and an energy consumption of 3.21 kWh m⁻³. Under these
525 conditions, the system allows to obtain an [•]OH concentration of 3.11 μM, an AMX
526 mineralization efficiency of 57.9% and a fecal coliforms inactivation of 90%. The
527 proposed reactor is a promising modular technology that can be used as tertiary
528 treatment to remove contaminants of emerging concern and for the disinfection of
529 wastewaters.

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715 **Declarations:**

716

717 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

718 Not applicable.

719

720 **Consent for publication**

721 Not applicable.

722

723 **Availability of data and materials**

724 Not applicable.

725

726 **Competing interests**

727 The authors declare no competing interests and that there are no conflicts of interests
728 regarding the publication of this work.

729

730 **Funding**

- 731 • Mexican Council for Science and Technology; CONACYT (Grant No.
732 PENTA2019-1-303758 and CB-2016-01-285309).
- 733 • Ministry for Education, Science, Technology and Innovation of CDMX
734 (SECTEI/259/2019).
- 735 • Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (Grant No. OPP1156657).

736

737 **Authors' contributions**

- 738 • Josué Daniel García-Espinoza: Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis.
- 739 • Irma Robles: Investigation, Methodology, Formal analysis.
- 740 • Alfonso Durán-Moreno: Investigation, Formal analysis, Supervision
- 741 • Luis A. Godínez: Conceptualization, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Project
742 administration, Funding acquisition.

743

744 **Acknowledgements**

745 The authors express their gratitude to the Mexican Council for Science and Technology;
746 CONACYT (Grant No. PENTA2019-1-303758 and CB-2016-01-285309), the Ministry for
747 Education, Science, Technology and Innovation of CDMX (SECTEI/259/2019) and to the
748 Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (Grant No. OPP1156657), for their financial support
749 of this work.